

From Bio-Big Bang to Bio-Cosmos in a Unified Darwinian String theory

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Abstract: In this research, we unify theory of evolution in biology with string theory in cosmology and propose a unified Darwinian string theory. In this theory, first a zero dimensional manifold decays into two types of closed strings, one generating cosmos and another producing biosystems. This event is called bio-big bang in a biocosmos. Cosmic closed strings decay into cosmic open strings. Some of these strings produce dimensions, universes and anti-universes. Some others create planets, stars, matters and anti-matters. Bio-closed strings decay into open bio-strings. These strings create biological matters like DNAs in universes, biological anti-matters like anti-DNAs in anti-universes and biological mixtures of matters and anti-matters within center of planets. Summing over charges of these three groups of biological matters is zero. These biological matters exchange states with each other and form a triangle of life. Each gene of a DNA acts like the receiver or sender of radio waves. To control exchanging waves between genes on planets, anti-genes in extra dimensions and genes or anti-genes within the center of planets, three types of neuronal circuits are emerged. A collection of these neurons produce neural network within the brain. When a creature is died or turn off, its DNA's states are transformed into center of planets or anti-universes. If DNA of a dead cell is located within an egg of a female, neurons of her brain take signals relating to dead cells from the center of planet, transform to the egg cell and reproduce creature or cells again. If some neurons are hurt and a part or all the brain is died, the best way is connecting a system of heart-brain to it's related heart. In these conditions, some waves are sending from biological system within the planet, taken by neurons of second system, transform to the heart of that patient, reprogram blood cells and produce new neurons within the initial brain. On the other hand, exchanging of waves between bio-system within the center of planets and DNAs on it depends on the location of creatures and thus, animals and humans have different shapes in each point of planet. In addition to these biological effects, biological system within the center of planet produce its magnetic field and temperature so. Because each gene is built from charged particles and by motion of them during orbiting of planet around star or in

cosmos, a current is appeared. Each current produces a magnetic field around the planet and summing over all fields results in producing known magnetic field within the center of planet. Also, some metals within the planet play the role of mirror and induce some anti-genes. In addition, some anti-genes are induced from extra dimensions. These two groups of anti-genes produce negative currents and magnetic fields in opposite direction respect to the magnetic field of genes. Consequently, magnetic fields of genes and anti-genes cancel effect of each other and total magnetic field of planet shrinks to known values. On the other hand, temperature depends on the energy of current and this energy decreases from infinity at center to lower values on the boundary and thus temperature is huge at center. Also, this temperature is reduced by currents of anti-genes and achieve to known values on the planet. Thus, this theory is in agreement with both biology and cosmology in a biocosmos.

I. Introduction

Up to day, science was divided into two separate main subjects and many sub-subjects. These main subjects are 1: Cosmology which considers the origin and evolutions of cosmos. 2. Biology which considers the origin and evolutions of bio-systems. These two subjects have considered separately and there isnt any theory to unify them. The best model for cosmology has been proposed by string theory and the best model for biology has been suggested by Darwin's theory. String theory considers evolutions of cosmos and predicts that the origin of all cosmological objects like black holes, stars, planets and even universes are some highly excited strings [1-4]. Also, this theory assumes that world has eleven dimensions and many lower dimensional branes which on each of them, one or more universes live. For example, our universe lives on a four dimensional brane and interacts with one anti-universe on another brane [5,6]. On the other hand, Darwin's theory suggested a model of evolutions for biological systems and considers the process of developing of Human and animals from single cell creatures [7,8]. Now, the question arises that how we could unify these two main theories in one?

In this research, we propose a unified Darwinian string theory which considers evolutions of a bio-cosmos from a bio-big bang to the present era. This model shows that the origin of bio-matters and cosmos are some closed strings which are emerged by decaying a zero-dimensional manifold. These strings decay into

open strings which some of them produce cosmos including universe and anti-universe and planets and some others create three types of biological matters on planets, within the center of it and in anti-universes. These three types of bio-systems exchange waves with each other and control programming and reprogramming of cells. Also, these bio-matters are the main cause of high temperature at the center of planet and its magnetic field.

The outline of this paper is as follows: In section II, we consider formation of bio-cosmos from strings. In section III, we show effects of bio-cosmos on programming and reprogramming of cells and emergence of neuronal circuits. In section IV, we calculate the temperature, magnetic field and energy within the center of planet by using concepts of bio-systems.

II. Emergence of biocosmos from strings

In this section, we unify cosmos and life in a new model and show that the origin of both of them are the same. To this aim, we present three stages for evolutions of bio-cosmos :

First, a zero-dimensional manifold decays into two groups of closed strings. One group produce cosmos and called cosmic closed strings. Second group create biological matters and called bio-closed strings (See figure 1).

Fig1. A zero-dimensional manifold decays into cosmic and bio-closed strings.

Second: Cosmic closed string decay into 1-dimensional open strings. Some of these strings join to each other and form dimensions. For example, a two-dimensional page is built from joining two 1-dimensional open strings. A three-dimensional manifold is formed from joining three 1-dimensional strings. These open strings form two manifolds. On one of them, our universe lives and on

another one, an anti-universe lives. Some other cosmic open strings join to each other and form planets, stars and other cosmological objects. Also, some cosmic open strings connect a universe and an anti-universe. One end of these strings produce matters in universe and another end produces anti-matters with opposite charge (See figure 2).

Fig 2: Emergence of cosmos from strings

Third: Second group of closed strings decay into bio-open strings. They form hexagonal and pentagonal manifolds of DNAs.

Hexagonal and pentagonal manifolds join and form three groups of biological systems like DNAs, one group lives within the center of planets, second group lives on the planets and third group lives in extra dimensions on anti-universe branes.

Three groups of DNAs form triangle of life which control evolutions of bio-systems in a universe and it's related anti-universe (See figure 3).

Fig 3: Emergence of triangle of life from strings

III. The role of bio-cosmos in programming and reprogramming of cells and the emergence of neuronal circuits

Until now, it has been shown that there are three types of biological systems. One system includes DNAs and other bio-matters on planets. Another type is a system including anti-DNAs in anti-universes. Third system contains DNAs and anti-DNAs within the center of planets. Summing over charges of these bio-matters is equal to zero (the charge of a closed string) . This means that these three biological systems are partner of each other (See figure 4).

Fig 4 : N DNAs on planet, M-N DNAs and anti-DNAs within the center of planets and M anti-DNAs in anti-universe

Each gene may be turn off or turn on by repressors. Previously, it has been shown that each turning on gene acts like a receiver or sender of radio waves. To receive or send these signals, some neuronal circuits are emerged (See figure 5).

Fig5: Each gene produces a neuronal circuit within the brain

Some of neuronal circuits correspond to genes on planets, some others are related to genes within the center of planets and other neurons are connected to anti-genes in extra dimensions on anti-universe. A collection of these neuronal circuits form the neural network within the brain (See figure 6).

Fig 6: Three groups of neurons corresponding to DNAs on planets, within the center of planets and in anti-universe form the brain

If some neurons are hurt, a brain may be died. In these conditions, signals of DNAs within the center of planet (partners of dead DNA) can be used in recovery of dead brain. If we connect heart of patient to the heart of a healthy patient, DNAs within the center of planet send its signals into neurons of the brain in healthy person. These signals are transformed from brain to the heart and then heart and brain of patient, reprogram some cells like blood [10-12] and produce new neurons within the brain of patient. Thus, some new neuronal circuits are emerged and dead brain becomes alive (See figure 7).

Fig 7: Reproduction of dead neurons by connecting second system of heart-brain to the heart of a patient

If a creature like a human is died, states of its DNA transforms into anti-universe or center of planet and again summing over charges of DNAs is zero. These states can be recovered and dead cell become alive. To this aim, dead DNA should be located in egg cells of a female. In these conditions, neurons of female exchange waves with DNAs within the center of planet, take information

about dead creature and transform it to the egg cell. Then, egg cell uses of these waves and information for reprogramming dead DNA, its replication and reproduction of new cells of a dead creature (See Figure 8) . Consequently, dead creature is reproduced again.

Fig 8: Reproduction of a human from a dead cell

To test the model, we can reprogram dead cells of a bird. To this aim, we can do below stages

1. We choose some of dead chickens in a Slaughterhouse and extract some cells of their lungs
2. We inject dead cells into some of egg cells of some living chickens.
3. We pour some amount of water in some vessels or tubes and put a plastic on it. Then, we put egg cells on the plastic and create some small holes such as molecules of water could evaporate and provide needed wet for egg cells. Next, we put another plastic on the head of tubes or vessels.

4. We put vessels into an incubator and keep them at 38⁰ C for two days.
5. We transform injected egg cells to reproductive system of chickens.
6. We connect injected egg cells and non-fertilized egg cells to an scope like oscilloscope or RadioSkypipe and take their signals (See figure 9).

In this experiment, we took signals of injected egg cells and non-fertilized cells within the reproductive system of chickens. We can have below results

1. By passing time, radiated signals of injected cells grow, turn over a maximum and reduce to lower values.
2. By passing time, radiated signals of non-fertilized egg cells grow and tend to a constant value (See figure 10)

This experiment shows that the shape of radiated signals of injected egg cells is completely different from non-fertilized cells. Both of egg cells are under similar conditions. Thus, the probability for this difference could be reprogramming of dead cells. On the other hand, injected and non-fertilized egg cells which were putting within reproductive cells should be connected into neurons and vessels of carrier. If this connection doesn't occur correctly, reprogramming will be stopped (See figure 10) .

Fig 9: Suggesting a mechanism for reproduction of a dead bird by reprogramming a dead cell

Fig 10: Comparing simulated signals of fertilized egg cells with non-fertilized egg cells

IV: Magnetic field and Temperature within the center of a rotating planet

Until now, we have argued about effects of biological system within center of planet on the evolution of life. However, this system could be main cause of the emergence of magnetic field and temperature within the center of planet. Because, each planet orbits around itself and also around an star like sun. During these motions, DNAs and other biological materials within the core move . These matters are built from charged particles and thus by their motions, some currents are emerged. These currents produce a huge amount of magnetic field and energy within the center. This energy has a direct relation with temperature and as a result a high temperature is emerged within the center of planet (See figure 11). We can formulate these events. We can write:

Fig 11: Emergence of currents by motion of charged particles within the center of planet

$$i_n(r) = q_n(r)v_n(r) \quad (1)$$

Where " i_n ", " q_n ", " v_n " are current, charge and velocity of each gene within the center of core respectively. Summing over all currents in each radius of center can be obtained as:

$$I(r) = \sum_{n=1}^N i_n(r) \quad (2)$$

This current produces a magnetic field at an special point or radius:

$$B(r) \sim \frac{\mu_0 I(r)}{2r} \quad (3)$$

Energy of this magnetic field depends on the radius. Energy of system within the center of planet can be calculated by summing over energy densities of magnetic fields:

$$E(r) \propto \int_V \frac{B^2(r)}{2\mu_0} \quad (4)$$

This energy has a direct relation with temperature :

$$T(r) \propto \frac{E(r)}{K_B} \quad (5)$$

Above equation shows that temperature within the center of planet depends on radius. This temperature has large values near $r=0$ and decreases by increasing distance from center.

On the planet like earth, the total number of humans currently living was estimated to have reached 7.7 billion people as of April 2019.. On the other hand, scientists concluded that the average human body contains approximately 37.2 trillion cells. If we assume that each cell has a DNA and each DNA may have 20000 genes, we can assume that only for human, there are more than 10^{25} genes on the planet. On the other hand, these genes maybe in relation with 10^{25} anti-genes in extra dimensions. Totally, 10^{50} states maybe produced by entanglement of these genes. If all of these states, genes and anti-genes are imaged within the center of earth, their motions produce a huge current. This current produces a large amount of energy and temperature. In figure 12, we assume that charges and currents of genes don't depend on the radius and by using equation (5) estimate temperature for the center of planet. It is observed that temperature is infinity at $r=0$ and decreases to 6200 as predicted by geophysics. However, these calculations could be applied only for the center of planet and we couldn't use them on planet so.

Fig 12: Temperature of center of planet in terms of its radius

Maybe this question arises that why these huge magnetic field and temperature couldn't be observed around the planet. This is because that in addition of genes, there are some anti-genes within the center of planets. These anti-genes maybe induced by mirroring of genes within metal core of planets or by some biological centers in extra dimensions. These anti-genes produce negative currents and magnetic fields with opposite direction respect to currents and fields of genes and cancel their effects. We have:

$$I_{On Planet} = I_{Gene} - I_{Anti-Gene} = \sum_{n=1}^N i_{n,gene}(r) - \sum_{n=1}^M i_{n,anti-gene}(r) \quad (6)$$

$$B_{On Planet} = N B_{Gene} - M B_{Anti-Gene} \propto Constant \quad (7)$$

$$FOR \quad M \approx N \quad B_{On Planet} \propto 25 - 65 \text{ MicroTesla}$$

$$T_{On Planet} = \frac{(N E_{Gene} - M E_{Anti-Gene})}{K_B} \propto Constant \quad (8)$$

$$\text{FOR } M \approx N T_{\text{On Planet}} \propto 250 - 300^{\circ} \text{ K}$$

Where "N" and "M" are number of genes and anti-genes respectively. For this reason, reverse to the center, magnetic field and temperature on the planet have constant and low values.

Fig 13: Currents of anti-genes cancel effects of currents of genes.

Now, we can response to this question that why shapes of people depends on the region which they live. For example Chinese people have different face respect to European ones. One of main reasons for this difference may be differences in radiating electromagnetic fields at each point of earth. These fields are emerged by genetic currents within the center of planet, taken by neurons within the brain of mother, transform into egg cells and help to program cells (See figure 14).

Fig 14 : Emergence of different shapes due to difference in radiated electromagnetic field in each point of earth

Conclusion

In this paper, we have generalized theory of evolution in biology to cosmology and shown that the origins of life and cosmos are the same. In fact, we define a biocosmos which its evolution begins from decaying a zero-dimensional manifold into bio-closed strings and cosmic closed strings at a bio-big bang. Cosmic closed strings decay into open strings. Open strings are one-dimensional object with two opposite charges in two ends. One end of each open string produces matters and another end creates anti-matters. By joining two open strings, a page is emerged and by joining three open strings, a three dimensional manifold like a universe or an anti-universe is produced. Some other open strings make planets, stars and other cosmological objects. On the other hand, bio-closed strings decay into bio-open strings. These strings join to each other and form hexagonal and pentagonal manifolds. These manifolds join to each other and build biological matters like DNAs on planets in a universe, anti-DNAs in anti-universe and DNAs + anti-DNAs within the center of planets. Charge of initial bio-closed string is equal to summing over charges of bio-matters on planets in a universe, bio-anti-matters in an anti-universe and bio-matter and anti-matter within the center of planets. These bio-matters exchange waves with each other and form a triangle for life. To receive or send waves of each gene in a bio-system, a neuronal circuit is emerged. Thus, there is three

types of neuronal circuits depending on genes on planets, anti-genes in anti-universe and genes or anti-genes within the center of planet. These circuits control programming and reprogramming of cells. For example, if we put DNA of a dead animal within the egg cell of a female, needed information for its turning on is transformed from its partner within the center of planet to the neurons in the brain of female and then to the egg cell. Consequently, DNA becomes alive and begins to reproduction of initial animal. On the other hand, if some neurons in a brain are died, exchanging waves between elements of triangle of life is stopped. To recover these neurons, a second heart-brain is connected to initial heart-brain axis and exchanged waves between bio-system within the center of planet and neurons in second brain help to reprogram blood cells and emergence of new neurons. Maybe this question arises that why shapes of human and animals depends on their location on planets. For example, Chinese people have different shapes respect to European ones. Maybe the reason for these differences is the dependency of exchanging waves between neurons and bio-system within the center of planet on the location of creatures. This model not only explains the biological events but also helps us to understand nature. For example, by moving planets or orbiting them, charged particles of bio-system form some currents. These currents are the main responsible for the magnetic field of planet and it's temperature within the center of planet. On the other hand, some metals have the role of mirror and produce currents in opposite directions respect to initial ones. These currents reduce the effect of genetic currents and produce a constant value of magnetic field around the planet.

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